

Analysis of the Capacity of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative in Eastern Province/Kisangani Antenne to Meet its 2013-2014 Objectives

Benjamin MALIKIDOGO KABARE and Fabrice ABIBU MATALI

Abstract:- This study on the analysis of the means of the Extractive Industries transparency Initiative, Kisangani chapter in the Eastern Province is of capital importance in the framework of good governance in the Democratic Republic of Congo. We want to know if, and only if, the resources made available to the EITI Kisangani Chapter enable it to achieve its objectives effectively and/or efficiently.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Democratic Republic of Congo is a country identified as being potentially very rich in various natural resources, particularly mining; but, unfortunately, it is classified as a highly indebted poor country, despite current efforts¹ at economic growth. In this perspective, the development of the Democratic Republic of Congo and that of its various provinces, notably the Oriental Province, can largely rely on the contribution of various public and private revenues, particularly in the extractive industries sector. Hence the importance of researching the EITI as an organisation in terms of its means of action to achieve its objectives.

YACHIR shows that "the development of large-scale mining activity coincides here with the beginning of the Leninist phase of imperialism, based on the constitution of industrial and banking monopolies, the exploitation of capital and the sharing of the world between the metropolises."²

From this point of view, our problematic revolves around the following four questions: What is the functional structure of the EITI in the Eastern Province? What is the distribution of the personnel who run this functional structure according to number, gender and the studies carried out? From 2013 to 2014, did the Kisangani EITI office receive equipment and a substantial budget for its operations? From 2013 to 2014, what were the achievements and constraints of the Kisangani EITI in Oriental Province? What prospects can be envisaged for its promotion?

With regard to the questions of our problematic, our working hypotheses revolve around the following

considerations: The functional structure of the EITI, which is still in its infancy in Province Orientale, is embryonic and provisionally limited to the Kisangani Antenna; the distribution of staff in terms of numbers, gender and studies carried out, in the functional structure of the Kisangani EITI-Antenna, is still insufficient; we estimate that from 2013 (the date of its establishment) to 2014, the Kisangani EITI-Antenna would have benefited from equipment and a budget that was not sufficient for its operation; from 2013 to 2014, we believe that the EITI's achievements would not have been satisfactory because of its recent establishment, which requires time to raise awareness of its objectives among the companies and financial authorities concerned, and also because of the constraints that would be even more significant in terms of buildings, material equipment and qualified personnel, on the other hand, the prospects that could be envisaged are essentially political, administrative, legal and ethical.

Our research is aiming at :

- Identifying the functional structure of the EITI in Oriental Province;
- Presenting the distribution of the personnel who run this functional structure according to number, gender and studies carried out, on the one hand, and the material and financial means of the EITI in the Eastern Province, on the other hand, in relation to its objectives;
- Examining the human, material, technical and financial resources of the EITI-Kisangani Office in the Eastern Province in relation to its objectives;
- Evaluating the achievements, constraints and prospects of the EITI in Oriental Province, with regard to its objectives and the means used;
- Considering the prospects for promoting the EITI in this Province.

Our research has two folds interest, notably scientific and practical. On the scientific level, this work is a contribution to disciplines such as management and the theory of organisations.

In the framework of this research we have opted for the use of the functional method by using the Parsonian scheme of structural-functional analysis

¹ Research Assistant at the Institut des Recherches Sociales Appliquées (IRSA) of University of Kisangani in the Democratic Republic of Congo.
benjmalikidogo@gmail.com

² M., MATATA PONYO, DRC : *L'éveil économique national*, Primature, Address of the Prime Minister to the Congolese Senate, Kinshasa, 10 December 2012, pp.1-22.

³ F., YACHIR, *Enjeux miniers en Afrique*, Édition Karthala, paris, 1987, p.14.

To carry out this study, we used two types of techniques, namely: the data collection technique and the results interpretation technique. As regards data collection, we used the technique of direct observation, the documentary technique and the free interview.

❖ GENERALITIES

This first chapter is devoted to general information and consists of two sections. The first section deals with the clarification of concepts and the second section focuses on the presentation of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative.

➤ Clarification Of Concepts

In any scientific work, conceptual clarification is necessary to enable the researcher to clarify the meaning of the concepts used in order to avoid misinterpretation. The following concepts need to be clarified: analysis, means, initiative, transparency, extractive industries, Eastern Province and objective.

➤ Analysis

Analysis is the intellectual process of breaking down a whole into its constituent parts and establishing the relationships between them.³

➤ Means

The means is what is used to achieve a result, an end.⁴

➤ Initiative

The initiative is an action of a person who proposes, undertakes, organises by being the first.⁵

➤ Transparency

Etymologically, transparency comes from the Latin word Trans, which means beyond, through and parere, to appear, to show oneself.

In the literal sense, transparency is the character of that which is transparent, which allows light to pass through it, allowing shapes and colours to be seen. Translucency, on the other hand, only transmits light.

Figuratively speaking, the word "transparency" is used to describe a social practice guided by sincerity and perfect accessibility of information in areas that concern public opinion. It is also the concern to account for an activity, to acknowledge mistakes. The primary objective of transparency is to establish a relationship of trust. It is opposed to opacity.⁶

➤ Extractive Industries

Any unit involved in the extraction, processing and marketing of any mineral, petroleum and forestry product.

Companies, trading posts and trading centres are to be considered as part of the extractive industries.⁷

The extractive industries are defined as the exploitation of natural mineral resources in a solid, liquid or gaseous state in the ground and subsoil, including underwater. Extraction maybe carried out by open pit, underground, by well, etc.

The extractive industries include the operations necessary for the marketing of mineral products: concentration of ores, liquefaction of natural gas, agglomeration of solid fuels, for example.

These operations are often carried out by the units that carry out the extraction and/or are located near the site.

These first three divisions concern the extraction of energy products (coal, lignite and turbo, hydrocarbons, uranium ore); the next two concern the extraction of non-energy products (metal ores, various minerals and quarry products).

Some of the technical operations in this section, particularly for the extraction of hydrocarbons, may be carried out on behalf of third parties by specialized units providing services.

Mining and quarrying excludes the processing of extracted products (manufacturing). It does not include prospecting (74.2c) or preparation of mineral sites (45.1b) when these activities are carried out for third parties. Mineral exploration gives rise to embedded assets that are tradable as such. Finally, the collection and distribution of water falls under a specific division (41), while the production of table water goes with the beverage industry (15.9s).⁸

II. ANALYSIS OF THE CAPACITY OF THE EXTRACTIVE INDUSTRIES TRANSPARENCY INITIATIVE IN THE EASTERN PROVINCE

In this chapter we have three main sections, namely: analysis of human resources, analysis of material resources and analysis of financial resources.

A. Analysis of Human Resources

➤ Quantitative aspect

From this point of view, we highlight the number of members of the EITI-Kisangani branch. The latter has a staff of five people, including four men and one woman.

➤ Qualitative aspect

This sub-section looks at the educational background of the EITI-Kisangani staff and their functions.

⁴ Robert pou tous, dictionnaire de la langue française, Paris, 1994, p.38.

⁵ Idem, p.748.

⁶ Idem, p.607.

⁷ www.toupie.org/Dictionnaire/Transparence.htm, le 23/06/2014 at 1:30 pm.

⁸ Synthesis of the EITI-DRC report 2007, august 2010, p.6.

⁹ Insee-Definitions and Methods-Naf rev.1, 2003-section C mining and quarrying on 20/06/2014 at 11:48

The qualifications of the five men and one woman mentioned above, employed at the Kisangani EITI Office, are as follows:

- One man is a capacity building officer. He is a university professor. He coordinates the activities of the Kisangani EITI Office in Province Orientale;
- Another man is in charge of data collection, head of the Antenna. He has a master's degree in forestry from the Faculty of Science;
- Another man is in charge of communication. Another man is in charge of communication. He has a degree in law;
- Another man is a secretary and public relations officer. Another man is a secretary and in charge of public relations. He has a degree from the Agronomic Faculty Institute of YANGAMBI (IFA);
- Finally, a woman is a surface technician. She is a graduate of the Institut Supérieur de Commerce.

Table 1: Synoptic table of the configuration of the staff of the EITI-Kisangani Office in Oriental Province

N°	OFFICE	NUMBER STAFF		STUDIES DONE
		MEN	WOMAN	
1	Data collection unit, head of the Antenna	1	-	Master's degree in forestry
2	Capacity building unit	1	-	PhD in SPA
3	Communication Unit	1	-	Bachelor of Law
4	Secretary and public relations	1	-	IFA Agricultural Engineer
5	Surface technician	-	1	SAI graduate
Total		4	1	5
Percentages		80%	20%	100%

Source: data from our surveys

B. Analysis of Material And Technical Resources

➤ *Material resources*

In this sub-section, we highlight the movable and immovable assets of EITI-Kisangani. EITI-Kisangani does not have its own building. It is housed in the EX-SODIAZ building in Kisangani, the capital of Oriental Province. With regard to the means of transport for staff to reach stakeholders, EITI does not yet have a vehicle. The EITI-Kisangani office also has some good quality movable property, including tables, office chairs, overhead projector, lap top, desk, cupboard, etc.

➤ *Technical means*

It is necessary to highlight the technical materials that the EITI-Kisangani has for its functioning. In terms of computer equipment, each office has computer equipment such as: computer, photocopier, scanner and printer. EITI-

Kisangani also has a Connection Antenna which facilitates research, correspondence and contacts between EITI staff in order to disseminate information to all countries that have implemented the EITI process.

C. Analysis of Financial Resources

➤ *BUDGET 2011-2013*

Within this framework, the EITI-DRC Executive Committee has put in place a three-year action plan for 2011-2013 which includes the necessary activities to design of a 2012 EITI-DRC Report by 31/12/2013 for publication, improving on some of the recommendations made by EITI International during the publication of the 2010 EITI-DRC Report and hoping to validate the 2011 Report to be promised as a compliant country.

In order to maintain the implementation of the EITI-DRC process, EITI-DRC has set up a three-year work plan amounting to 4,780,748 \$⁹ from which all the provincial EITI Technical Secretariats operate on the basis of operating costs (on a needs basis).

II.3.1.1. Table 2: Summary table of the 2011-2013 EITI-DRC budgets

Donors	amounts	Percentage
PROMINES	795.950	17%
MDTF	500.000	10%
GOVERNMENT	2.613.993	55%
PARTNER	870.800	18%
TOTAL	4.780.748%	100%

Source: Three-Year Action Plan 2011-2013

The elaboration of the EITI-DRC 2011 report is embodied in the roadmap for the publication of the EITI-DRC report by 31/12/2013 to facilitate the collection of data and the sensitisation of the scoping study to hope to be promised EITI compliant country.

➤ *2014 Budget*

To this end, the EITI-DRC National Executive Committee has put in place an annual work plan for 2014 that includes all the activities necessary for the validation of the 2012 EITI-DRC Report. In order to maintain the implementation of the EITI DRC process, EITI DRC has put in place a three-year work plan amounting to \$3,824,550¹⁰ from which all EITI Technical Secretariats (provincial branches) operate on an as-needed basis.

The EITI-DRC annual work plan provided for the following :

- The government has to pay \$2,743,900 or 72% of the cost
- The partner \$585,650 or 15% and
- The MDTF 495,000 or 13%.

¹⁰ Three-year action plan 2011-2013.

¹¹ Annual work plan 2014

Table 3: Summary table of the 2014 EITI-DRC budget

Donors	Amounts	Percentage
Government	2.743.900 \$	72%
Partners	585.650 \$	15%
MDTF	495.000 \$	13%
Total	3.824.550	100%

Source: 2014 Work Plan.

Despite all this, there is a roadmap for the publication of the 2012 EITI-DRC report by 31/12/2014 and, to facilitate data collection and awareness raising capacity building of civil society and mining and oil companies for the scoping study as foreseen by EITI International.

Table 4: Summary table of EITI-Kisangani's resources in Province Orientale

Means		
Materials	Techniques	Financials
Office tables	2 computers	-
Meeting tables	2 photocopiers	-
Office chairs	1 scanner	-
Meeting chairs	1 printer	-
Cabinet	Overhead projector	-
Building rental	Undular	-
Hire of self-propelled	Laptop	-
-	-	The department concerned did not give me the financial information

Source: Data from our surveys

III. INTERPRETATION OF THE RESULTS

In this chapter, our work is divided into six sections: on objectives, means, achievements, constraints and proposals for improvement, respectively.

A. On Objectives

The EITI-Kisangani Chapter in Oriental Province from 11 March 2013 to 2014 has effectively pursued its objectives, namely:

- To strengthen good governance by improving transparency and accountability in the extractive industries sector through the collection, verification, reconciliation and publication of all payments made by public and private companies to the state.
- Ensure the publication and dissemination of payments made by extractive companies and related revenues received by government departments;
- Make this information accessible and understandable to the general public;
- To promote the proper use of this wealth so that it is an engine of economic growth and contributes to sustainable development and poverty reduction.

B. Concerning The Functional Structure

Our hypothesis that the functional structure of the EITI, still in its infancy, in Oriental Province would be embryonic and provisionally limited to the Kisangani Antenna has been confirmed. Indeed, the Oriental Province, which is made up of four districts (Ituri, Haut-Uélé, Bas-Uélé and Tshopo), currently has only one EITI Antenna, located in the city of Kisangani.

C. Concerning Human Resources

Our assumption that the number, gender and educational distribution of staff in the functional structure of the EITI-Kisangani was still inadequate was disproved. Indeed, the organic staffing for the functioning of the provincial committees is set at 5 members per province. The EITI-Kisangani Office in Orientale Province actually functions with a staff of 5.

D. Concerning Material, Technical And Financial Means

We have also estimated that, from 2013 (date of its establishment) to 2014, the EITI-Kisangani would have benefited from equipment and a budget that was not substantial; for its operation, this hypothesis has not been confirmed either. Indeed, the EITI Technical Secretariat in Kinshasa has always responded satisfactorily to the material, technical and financial needs of the Kisangani EITI Office in Oriental Province. Nevertheless, we did not have access to the financial data.

E. Regarding Achievements And Constraints

Our hypothesis that from 2013 to 2014 the achievements of the EITI-Kisangani Office in Oriental Province would be unsatisfactory, due to its recent involvement which requires time to raise awareness of its objectives among the companies and financial authorities concerned, and that the constraints would be even more significant in terms of buildings, material equipment and qualified personnel, has not been confirmed.

➤ ACHIEVEMENTS

• Awareness-raising of

Stakeholders Stake holders in Oriental Province were made aware of the implementation of the roadmap for the publication of the EITI-DRC 2011 report adopted in June 2013 by the EITI-DRC Executive Committee. In relation to this roadmap, the Province's stakeholders were also made aware of the international framing study called Fair Links led by Mr AnthoMelard de Fenardent.

The first draft of the scoping study report was presented at the MEMLING Hotel in Kinshasa on Wednesday, 14 August 2013 to members of the EITI-DRC Executive Committee, parliamentarians and media professionals.

In order to reach out to all stakeholders in the Eastern Province, the EITI-Kisangani Head of Office of the EITI-DRC Technical Secretariat, in collaboration with the provincial Ministers of Planning and of Natural Resources, Mines, Hydrocarbons and Forestry, took the initiative of hosting several televised awareness-raising programmes on

the scoping study for the publication of the 2011 EITI-DRC Report.

This activity of sensitisation of stakeholders through RTNC-TV/Kisangani had not only the total involvement but also the participation of the Provincial Government of the Eastern Province.

Following the letter n° CAB/MIN.PROV/PBP/PO/AKMB/160/2013 of 26 June 2013 addressed to the Provincial Director of RTNC by the Provincial Minister of Planning, a one-hour slot of the programme "Notre Congo" was granted to EITI-Kisangani in order to sensitise the stakeholders of the Eastern Province.

On Friday, 28 June 2013, from 20:00 to 21:00 on the set of RTNC-TV, their Excellencies the Provincial Minister of Planning, Mines, Hydrocarbons and Forests as well as the head of the EITI-Kisangani antenna had participated in the sensitisation of stakeholders on the implementation of the EITI process in the DRC through the programme "Notre Congo" which was presented by Mr Jean Stanis BILANGA, a journalist at RTNC-Kisangani.

• *THE SCOPING STUDY FOR THE PUBLICATION OF THE EITI-DRC REPORT 2011*

In this perspective, the scoping study will make it possible to define a realistic materiality threshold that will allow for a clear and permissive determination of the Extractive Companies, the financial flows as well as the contractual flows of significant benefits that must be taken into account in the publication of the EITI-DRC 2011 report.

In order to arrive at a realistic scoping study, the contribution of all stakeholders in the process at the provincial level is essential. On Saturday, 06 July 2013, the national coordinator of the EITI DRC technical secretariat sent an official letter bearing n°101/CN/EITI-DRC/ST/NG/2013 to His Excellency Mr Jean BAMANISA SAIDI, Governor of the Province Orientale, in order to obtain his involvement in the scoping study for the publication of the EITI DRC 2011 Report. In order to participate in the scoping study for the publication of the 2011 EITI-DRC report, the revenue department of the Eastern Province was required to make available to the Expert in charge of data collection of the EITI-Kisangani Office, before the deadline of Tuesday, 09 July 2013 information relating to the list of documents enabling the regulatory and fiscal framework in force in 2011 for the extractive sector to be established, the list of revenues collected by the DRPO from Extractive Companies in 2011, the list of Extractive Company acts registered by the DRPO with Extractive Companies in 2011 (detailed/company).

In the absence of the Governor of the Province on mission in Kinshasa, an instruction from the Provincial Minister of Planning, who was acting in his place, led the expert in charge of data collection and the EITI secretariat to Kisangani in order to meet with the Vice-Governor of Oriental Province, who was acting in his place, and hand over this official correspondence from the EITI technical secretariat.

To show the involvement of the provincial government in the scoping study for the publication of the EITI-DRC 2011 report:

- His Excellency the Vice-Governor of the Province had immediately sent a letter n°01/JBS/1021/CAB/PROGOU/PO/2013 to the Provincial Director of the DRPO, instructing him to make available to the Expert in charge of the collection of EITI data - Kisangani Office in Oriental Province the information requested by the scoping study for the publication of the EITI-DRC report;
- His Excellency the Provincial Minister of Natural Resources, Hydraulics, Electricity, Hydrocarbons, Mines and Forestry had also sent a letter N/REF: 456/ODP/cab/MIN.PROV/RNHEHMF/PO/2013 to the Head of the EITI Antenna in Kisangani. This correspondence mandated the latter, as the Expert in charge of data collection, to access information on Extractive Companies registered at the DRPO as taxpayers in 2011, which was requested by the EITI-DRC technical secretariat for the preparation of the scoping study report for the publication of the EITI-DRC 2011 report.

Following all these correspondences, the DRPO had made available to the Expert in charge of data collection of the EITI-Kisangani Office, the complete information on the list of documents allowing to establish the regulatory and fiscal framework in force in 2011 for the Extractive sector registered by the DRPO as a taxpayer in 2011 and the list of all the amounts collected by the DRPO from the Extractive Companies in 2011 partially provided.

This information was shared with His Excellency the Vice-Governor of Oriental Province before being transmitted to the EITI-DRC technical secretariat in Kinshasa.

In order to obtain the list of Extractive Companies and the financial and contractual flows of significant benefits, the EITI-Kisangani data collector worked with several financial authorities in the Province, namely the DGI, DGRAD and DGDA, but also with public services (such as the Provincial Division of Mines, the Provincial Coordination of the Environment and the Provincial Division of Hydrocarbons) and specialised services (such as the CEEC and SAESCAM).

This approach enabled the Expert to have access to basic information on the Extractive Companies operational in 2011 in Oriental Province, namely the list of mining and forestry companies, the list of artisanal timber exploiters, the list of cooperatives of artisanal timber exploiters, the list of precious materials purchase counters, the list of all the revenues collected from Extractive Companies, and the list of all the amount collected from Extractive Companies.

With regard to the Financial Regies, several pieces of information on the financial flows were provided to the data collector by the different Financial Regies. This information is presented for each Financial Authority concerned.

• **TRAINING**

In this regard, the Expert in charge of capacity building had finalised the guide for capacity building of stakeholders. In addition, he had concentrated his efforts on drawing up the Terms of Reference for the activities of his unit and contacting the stakeholders (members of civil society in Oriental Province and the Extractive Companies) for training.

• **COMMUNICATION**

As part of the scoping study on 26 July 2013, in collaboration with the head of the Provincial Office, the communication expert produced the script for the awareness-raising programme on the implementation of the EITI process in the DRC on 28 June 2013 with their Excellencies the Provincial Ministers of Planning and Mines and the head of the Provincial Office of the EITI-DRC technical secretariat.

On 4 July 2013, still in collaboration with the head of the EITI Antenna in Kisangani, the expert in charge of

communication produced the programme on the scoping study for the publication of the EITI-DRC 2011 report.

On 7 August 2013, the Communication Expert took part in a working session with the presentation of the programme, the aim of this session being to prepare for the EITI and we programme on Thursday, 8 August 2013.

• **PARTICIPATION IN WORKSHOPS, CONFERENCES AND RETREAT**

Concerning participation in workshops, conferences and retreats, during this period, the Head of the Chapter and the Communication Officer of the EITI-Kisangani Chapter were invited to several activities organised in the city of Kisangani.

The main activities in which these experts took part are listed respectively according to their date in the table below:

Table 5: Summary table of lists of relevant EITI-Kisangani activities in Province Oriental

Date	Location	Type of activity	Organizer
05 june 2013	Sale la fourchette boyomaise	World environment day	Provincial minister for the environment
20 june 2013	Sale fourchette la boyomaise	Tripartite meeting between the eastern province and two provinces of southern sudan	Governor of the eastern province
25 july 2013	Sale bourgeoise	Meeting of the provincial policy and development committee (PPDC)	Provincial planning minister
19 august 2013	Gradi-youth room	Reflection day on the problems and challenges in the mining sector in the eastern province	Civil society (ngdo prodaewi) with Christian Aid

Source: Quarterly progress report and monitoring of EITI implementation in Oriental Province.

➤ **CONSTRAINTS**

This section looks at the difficulties that the Kisangani EITI office is encountering in collecting data from extractive companies, financial regulators and in raising awareness among stakeholders.

According to the roadmap for the publication of the EITI-DRC report 2011 to 31 December 2013, the period from June to August will be used for awareness raising and capacity building of stakeholders on the implementation of the EITI process in the DRC. The televised awareness-raising programmes on the process conducted by the EITI-Kisangani Antenna Manager in collaboration with members of the Provincial Government were not enough to involve all stakeholders in Province Orientale.

The financial authorities and extractive companies are suspicious of the EITI process and do not facilitate the data collection agent to collect reliable data to report to the EITI-DRC national coordinator.

The lack of capacity building and insufficient awareness of stakeholders on the scoping study for the publication of the EITI-DRC 2011 report had a negative impact on the collection of information on Mining, Oil and Forestry Companies that could be included in the scoping report.

The information was not provided in its entirety by stakeholders in Oriental Province, despite the intervention of local authorities. In addition, the data collector was not able to provide an exhaustive list of significant benefit streams in Province Orientale. This work continues to this day.

Some public services, specialised services, financial authorities and extractive companies had refused to collaborate with the expert in charge of data collection, but following the involvement of the Provincial Government, they had finally collaborated. On several occasions, we visited the Provincial Ministers of Planning, Mines and Finance for their personal involvement in the collection of information on the province's extractive industries and their significant benefits treams.

F. Proposals For Impruvement

In view of the EITI-DRC process, the Kisangani EITI Office in the Eastern Province is still working within the vision of the EITI-DRC Technical Secretariat. In line with the activities of the roadmap for the publication of the EITI-DRC report 2011 to 31 December 2013, we propose these:

- The EITI DRC National Executive Committee in collaboration with the EITI DRC Technical Secretariat Coordinator should implement the roadmap for the

- publication of the next EITI DRC Report in real time to enable the provincial EITI DRC Technical Secretariat Offices to properly carry out the activities set out in the roadmap in accordance with the processes;
- And if the EITI DRC National Executive Committee implements the roadmap for the timely publication of the EITI DRC report, the future of the EITI DRC process will be guaranteed;
 - That the Government of the Democratic Republic of Congo provide the Executive Committee, the Technical Secretariat and the provincial branches with the necessary tools to enable them to build capacity for stake holder awareness of the EITI-DRC;
 - And that the governments of the Democratic Republic of Congo provide the Executive Committee, the Technical Secretariat and the provincial EITI-DRC Chapters with the appropriate buildings for their proper functioning.

IV. CONCLUSION

This is the conclusion of our study entitled: "Analysis of the means of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative in Oriental Province in relation to its objectives".

At the end of our research, we have come up with the following results:

- 1) Highlighting the objectives of the EITI-RDCongo and those of the EITI-Kisangani in the Eastern Province;
- 2) Concerning the functional structure of the EITI-Kisangani Office in Oriental Province, our initial hypothesis was confirmed. Concerning the achievements and constraints, our initial hypothesis was also not confirmed insofar as the EITI-Kisangani Office has, in one year of existence, carried out several achievements. Nevertheless, the constraints are, in part, linked to the recent establishment of the Kisangani Chapter in terms of awareness raising and data collection.
- 3) With regard to human, material, technical and financial resources, our initial hypothesis was invalidated. This hypothesis was invalidated insofar as the EITI Technical Secretariat in DRCongo has always responded satisfactorily to the needs of the EITI-Kisangani Chapter in Oriental Province.

Based on the above results, we suggest the following:

- a. Maintain links with the Extractive Companies of Oriental Province and the Financial Regies in order to accompany the Independent Administrator in the collection of declarations for the EITI-DRC 2012 Report;
- b. Maintain a good working relation ship with the Provincial Government and the Provincial Assembly for political support in the realisation of the roadmap for the publication of the EITI-DRC 2012 Report by 31 December 2014;
- c. Maintain a good working relation ship with civil society in Oriental Province in order to involve them in the realisation of the roadmap for the publication of the EITI-DRC 2012 Report by 31 December 2014;
- d. Strengthen awareness raising and capacity building activities for stakeholders on the collection of reports for the 2012 DRC-EITI Report.

- e. And develop communication actions towards stakeholders in the Eastern Province in line with the national strategic communication plan.

REFERENCES

- [1]. M., MATATA PONYO, DRC : *L'éveil économique national*, Primature, Address of the Prime Minister to the Congolese Senate, Kinshasa, 10 December 2012;
- [2]. F., YACHIR, *Enjeux miniers en Afrique*, Édition Karthala, Paris ;
- [3]. Robert pou tous, dictionnaire de la langue française, Paris, 1994 ;
- [4]. www.toupie.org/Dictionnaire/Transparence.htm, le 23/06/2014 at 1:30 pm;
- [5]. Synthesis of the EITI-DRC report 2007, August 2010;
- [6]. Insee-Definitions and Methods-Naf rev.1, 2003-section C mining and quarrying on 20/06/2014 at 11:48
- [7]. Three-year action plan 2011-2013;
- [8]. Annual work plan 2014.